

***A priori* confidence index for seasonal forecasts**

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1. Executive summary

Work package 4 of C3S2_MF_370 proposes to design a new tool for the interpretation of multi-model ensemble seasonal forecasts, consisting in a confidence index to be included whenever a new real-time forecast is issued (Task 4.3). The aim of the confidence index is to provide an *a priori* estimation of how correct the forecast will be against the verifying observations. The focus is set on European climate, defined by average near-surface temperature and accumulated precipitation over the next season, and the corresponding atmospheric circulation. This tool is intended to bring additional information in the preparation of the real-time seasonal forecast bulletins at Météo-France, and will be experimented shortly. This deliverable is the final document for Task 4.3. It is a follow-up of the intermediate milestone M4.3.1 issued in June 2023: while M4.3.1 is mostly focusing on confidence in a forecast of a single parameter such as a grid-point value, the present report elaborates on a confidence index for the spatial patterns of forecast anomalies over Europe.

2. Introduction

The main product of seasonal forecast bulletins issued by Météo-France consists in seasonal outlooks for near-surface temperature (T2m) and precipitation (RR) anomalies over Europe. These outlooks are synthesis maps featuring hand-drawn areas with the expected anomalies and a qualitative indication of how likely they are to occur. The synthesis maps are therefore a combination of numerical seasonal forecasts from the Copernicus Climate Change Services (C3S), and the forecasters' expert knowledge.

In this process, a quantitative estimate of how trustworthy the numerical forecasts are can be very useful to forecasters, both for the design of synthesis maps and for their communication to a wider audience. For instance, the synthesis maps could also feature a sort of “grade” on the expected quality of the provided information. This is the purpose of the present document, describing the elaboration of a confidence index to be computed whenever a new forecast is issued. The general idea is to define the confidence index as a “forecast” of the score that will be achieved by the C3S multi-model ensemble when verifying observations are available (i.e 4 months later for the forecasts of seasonal mean).

This work is therefore an attempt to apply to seasonal prediction the principle of “forecasting forecast skill” (Tennekes, 1986) – which has been investigated several times for short-range weather prediction (e.g Kalnay and Dalcher 1987, Palmer and Tibaldi 1988, Molteni and Palmer 1991, Wobus and Kalnay 1995). In these previous studies, the predictand is the forecast score itself, and the predictors quantify various properties of the forecasting context such as:

1. Consistency between members from the same ensemble forecast (Kalnay and Dalcher 1987, Palmer and Tibaldi 1988)
2. Consistency between forecasts from several institutions (Leslie and Holland 1990, Wobus and Kalnay 1995)
3. Consistency between consecutive forecasts with different initial conditions, valid over the same period (Molteni and Palmer 1991)

4. Persistence along the forecast, from initialization to target period (Chen 1989, Leslie and Holland 1990, Wobus and Kalnay 1995)
5. Amplitude of the forecast anomalies (Molteni and Palmer 1991, Wobus and Kalnay 1995)
6. Specific large-scale conditions related to forecast performance, determined from past forecasts (Molteni and Tibaldi 1988, Palmer and Molteni 1991)

Generally speaking, this points to the fact that confidence in a forecast can be strongly conditioned on consistency, that is to say agreement, between several sources of information. We decided to build on this aspect to define our confidence index, and more precisely on agreement between ensemble members (condition 1), and between different institutions (condition 2). This is done by considering a C3S multi-model as one large ensemble.

In the intermediate milestone M4.3.1, we mainly focused on confidence in the grid point forecasts by predicting whether the forecast tercile category is correct or not. Then, this final deliverable focuses more closely on confidence in the overall spatial pattern of anomalies that is predicted, rather than grid point information. However, these two approaches can be complementary for seasonal forecast bulletins, and could both be taken into account in a real-time framework.

After a quick presentation of the data (Section 3), Section 4 discusses the general principles we adopted to define and evaluate the confidence index. Section 5 describes the implementation to the maps of 500 hPa geopotential, temperature and precipitation anomalies over Europe, and includes an assessment of the role of the climate trend. Using the example of ENSO, Section 6 discusses the relationship between the proposed confidence index and the strength of a strong preconditioning driver bringing seasonal predictability. Section 7 makes a cross-comparison between the grid point approach from Milestone M4.3.1 and the new spatial approach of the present deliverable, while Section 8 illustrates the results on recent real-time forecasts. A conclusion is provided in Section 9.

3. Data

Seasonal forecast data follows the same structure as in M4.3.1 and is retrieved from the Copernicus Climate Data Store on the common 1° archiving grid. We use the reforecasts from the six models CMCC, DWD, ECMWF, Météo-France, NCEP and UKMO, targeting the three-month seasonal averages at a lead time of 1-month (LT1). Reforecasts are included for each initialization month over the common reforecast period 1994-2016, making a sample of 12 months x 23 years = 276 start dates. Note that reforecast year 1993 is also available on the CDS but is not included due to a consistency issue in the climate trend for Météo-France seasonal forecasts. The ensemble sizes of the 6 models and the resulting multi-model is shown in Table 1.

While M4.3.1 only focused on the near-surface temperature parameter (T2m), this report also includes analysis on precipitation (RR, accumulated over the three-month period) and Z500. T2m and RR are considered on the European domain 29.5°W-40.5°E; 30.5°N-70.5°N with sea grid points masked, leading to a total of 1,287 grid points. Z500 is considered over a larger domain encompassing Europe and the North Atlantic: 85.5°W-35.5°E, 27.5°N-80.5°N. Reference data for verification

comes from the ERA5 reanalysis (Hersbach et al 2020) interpolated on the same 1° grid as seasonal reforecasts.

Model	CMCC	DWD	ECMWF	MF	NCEP	UKMO	Multi-model
Reforecast ensemble size	40	30	25	25	24	28	172
Real-time ensemble size	50	50	51	51	52	50	304

Table 1: Ensemble sizes of the six C3S models and the multi-model

4. What is a (good) confidence index?

4.1 Forecast score

In this work, we intend to design the confidence index as a single value predicting how “good” a given forecast will be, at the time it is issued and before the verifying observations are available. The confidence index relates to the definition of a “good” forecast, and therefore depends on the specific score S that is used for verification. The scores that are eligible to define a confidence index are only those that can be defined for a single forecast. Error scores such as Mean Absolute Error, Root Mean Square Error, Brier Score, RPS or CRPS meet this condition, and so do measures of spatial verification such as the Anomaly Correlation Coefficient (ACC, i.e spatial correlation of the anomaly patterns between forecast and observation). On the contrary, estimates of forecast skill over a full reforecast period, e.g based on temporal correlation or contingency tables, are excluded. The choice of the score itself depends on the aspect of forecast quality that is most important to the user. Once it is chosen, the confidence index is supposed to be a “forecast” of the score, and should therefore be homogeneous with it.

In the first part of M4.3.1 (Section 4), forecasts are considered at each grid point separately, and the score S is a binary value 0/1 indicating whether the forecast tercile category is correct or not. The corresponding confidence index, a real value between 0 and 1, expresses the probability that the forecast category matches the observed one, i.e that the score will be 1. In a second part of M4.3.1 (Section 5.2), we attempted to design a confidence index predicting the spatial ACC that the forecast would have against the upcoming observations. After further investigation, the proposed approach based on Predictable Components did not prove successful and was abandoned for the present report, but the score S to be predicted remains the spatial ACC. Indeed, it reflects the main quality of forecasts that is desirable for seasonal forecast bulletins, namely the correct positioning of anomalies over Europe and the Euro-Atlantic region.

4.2 Expected score based on a perfect model approach

The forecast score S is computed as a function of the forecast ensemble mean f_{em} and the verifying observation o : $S(f_{em}, o)$. While f_{em} is available in real-time when the forecast is issued, o is obviously not. However, if the forecast uncertainty is sufficiently well sampled by the ensemble distribution, the observation o should lie in the distribution defined by the forecast members f_i . Similarly, we may assume that $S(f_{em}, o)$ should lie in the distribution defined by the “perfect model” scores $S(f_{em}, f_i)$ between each member and the ensemble mean. In other words, the values of $S(f_{em}, f_i)$ define an “ensemble forecast” of the score. We use the mean of this “ensemble forecast”, denoted S_{pm} (where “pm” stands for “perfect model”) as a prediction of the actual score $S(f_{em}, o)$. The approach is summarized in Figure 1 for one particular example of forecast, when the considered score S is the ACC.

Figure 1: Distribution of the ACCs of T2m anomalies over Europe between the multi-model ensemble members and their ensemble mean. The mean of the distribution ACC_{pm} is indicated in red.

In this deliverable, the ensemble is the multi-model described in Section 3. The value of the “perfect model” score $S(f_{em}, f_i)$ reflects the agreement of member i with the ensemble mean. The average over all members, S_{pm} , can therefore be viewed as an indicator of overall agreement in the ensemble. Because the multi-model combines members from different institutions, the confidence index S_{pm} is connected to the first two criteria for confidence listed in the Introduction: 1) Consistency between members from the same ensemble forecast, and 2) Consistency between forecasts from several institutions.

The confidence index at grid point level from M4.3.1 is actually based on this perfect model score, when the score S is the binary value 0/1 for incorrect/correct forecast. If the score S is the spatial ACC as in the current deliverable, the definition of ACC_{pm} as the average of spatial correlations between several pairs of forecasts makes it close to the original predictor of forecast skill introduced by Kalnay and Dalcher (1987).

4.3 How to evaluate a confidence index

The relevance of the confidence index should be assessed over a large sample of reforecasts, to determine whether it would have been, on average, a good indication of forecast proficiency at issuance time. Since the confidence index is a “forecast”, it can be evaluated using any verification metric, and the verification data corresponds to the actual score against observations.

Here, we choose a metric assessing the property of a forecast called discrimination (Mason and Weigel, 2009), that provides an answer to the following question: given two forecasts f_1 and f_2 , and their corresponding confidence indices S_{pm}^1 and S_{pm}^2 such that $S_{pm}^1 < S_{pm}^2$, what is the chance that the actual scores S_1 and S_2 indeed verify the condition $S_1 < S_2$? In other words, we intend to quantify whether higher confidence implies a higher score when two forecasts are compared. Such a choice is motivated by the intended use of the confidence index in a real-time practice, where forecasters may ask if the current forecast is expected to be better, e.g. than last month’s or last year’s forecast at the same season.

The corresponding metric is the proportion of forecast pairs where the order is conserved between S and S_{pm} (concordant pairs). We use notation D where D stands for discrimination:

$$D = \frac{\text{Number of concordant pairs}}{\text{Total number of pairs}}$$

In the following sections, D will be expressed as a percentage of correctly ranked forecast pairs. D is also equivalent to the Kendall rank correlation coefficient τ between the confidence index S_{pm} and the score S along the reforecasts, according to the formula:

$$D = \frac{\tau + 1}{2}$$

Finally, D is also similar to the area under a ROC curve (see Mason and Weigel, 2009), and equals to 50% if there is no relation between the confidence index S_{pm} and the score S . Significance of D is assessed through significance of the corresponding Kendall τ with the dedicated ‘cor.test’ function in the R language. The null hypothesis of the test is that $\tau = 0$ (i.e. $D = 50\%$). Under this null hypothesis τ is supposed to be drawn from a predefined normal distribution depending on the verification sample. If the probability that $\tau = 0$ is less than 5% according to this distribution, the null hypothesis is rejected and D is considered significant at the 95% level.

Beyond the discriminative ability of the confidence index, another desirable property is a good calibration relative to the score S : from a user’s perspective, the confidence index S_{pm} of a given real-time forecast must directly indicate the actual value of S that can be expected. Calibration is assessed through a reliability diagram based on binning the values of the confidence index, from 0 to 1 by 0.1 in the present deliverable. The reliability diagram represents the average value of the score S , i.e. the expected score, for all forecasts when the confidence index S_{pm} is included in a specific bin. Contrary to discrimination evaluated by metric D , calibration of the confidence index can be improved by post-processing. In this deliverable, we use a linear regression of S against S_{pm} to define a re-calibrated version of the confidence index.

5. Confidence indices for spatial patterns

5.1 How good is the forecast of Z500, temperature and precipitation ACCs?

The confidence index predicting the value of the multi-model ACC is defined following the perfect model approach from Section 4.2 and is noted ACC_{pm} . Figure 2 shows the scatter plots of ACC_{pm} values against the actual ACC values for the three variables under study: Z500 over the Euro-Atlantic domain, T2m and RR over Europe. The actual ACC corresponds to verification of the multi-model against ERA5. In each scatter plot, there are as many dots as reforecasts, i.e 12 initialization months x 23 years = 276.

Figure 2: Scatter plots showing the actual ACC of the multi-model seasonal reforecasts (reference: ERA5) against the “perfect model” ACC_{pm} . The sample is the full reforecast (size 23 years x 12 initializations = 276). The domain for computation of ACC is the Euro-Atlantic domain for Z500, and Europe (land grid points only) for T2m and RR. The discrimination metric D is indicated with a * when significant at the 95% level. The linear regression of ACC against ACC_{pm} used for calibration is shown in red.

The scatter plots suggest that the confidence indices are partially able to distinguish forecasts with higher or lower ACCs. The discrimination metrics D defined in Section 4.3 are indicated at the bottom and quantify that ACC_{pm} provides the correct order of the actual ACCs for about 55 to 62% of forecast pairs. These values are always significant at the 95% level according to the dedicated test (see Section 4.3), but we note that the approach is more proficient for Z500 or T2m than for precipitation.

Figure 3: Reliability diagrams of the ACC_{pm} confidence indices predicting the actual ACC (reference: ERA5) for the three variables Z500 (Euro-Atlantic domain), T2m and RR (Europe domain, land grid points only). Bins are

defined from 0 to 1 by 0.1, and the coordinates correspond to the average values of ACC_{pm} and ACC within each bin. The proportions of forecasts in each bin are indicated in the diagrams. The diagram in red corresponds to a calibrated version of ACC_{pm} using the linear regressions illustrated in Figure 2. The sample is the full reforecast (size 23 years x 12 initializations = 276).

A visual inspection of the scatter plots shows that for Z500 and T2m, the highest values of ACC_{pm} are generally indicative of good forecasts, e.g. when ACC_{pm} is greater than 0.4 the actual ACC often exceeds 0.2. However, low values of ACC_{pm} do not necessarily mean that the forecast will be bad. In other words, ACC_{pm} mostly provides an indication of forecast performance when it exhibits high values: this is the main weakness such a confidence index.

Another indication from Figure 2 is that values of ACCs almost cover the full range from -1 to 1, while ACC_{pm} is positive and does not exceed 0.6 for Z500 and T2m, and 0.4 for precipitation. This is a consequence of defining ACC_{pm} as an “ensemble mean” of ACCs (see Section 4.2), preventing it to reach very high or low values. In other words, the ACC_{pm} confidence index may exhibit close-to-zero values suggesting no forecast performance, but will never reach significantly negative values indicating forecasts that are opposite to observations.

Calibration of ACC_{pm} is evaluated in the reliability diagrams from Figure 3. The blue curves represent how representative the raw ACC_{pm} are of the actual values of ACC, prior to any post-processing. The red curves are obtained with a re-calibrated version defined by the linear relationships indicated in Figure 2 and obtained through a linear regression of ACC against ACC_{pm} . Figure 3 shows that the raw ACC_{pm} indices are reasonably well calibrated for Z500 and T2m, although they exhibit some mismatches at their higher and lower values, where the Z500 ACC_{pm} tends to overestimate the actual ACC while the T2m ACC_{pm} is underestimating it. For these two variables, re-calibration through the linear regression does not bring a real added value. As for precipitation, ACC_{pm} is overestimating the actual ACC, a flaw which is corrected thanks to the linear re-calibration.

5.2 On the influence of climate change warming trend

Results from the previous section are obtained using temperature anomalies in the 1994-2016 reforecast period, with anomalies computed relative to the 1994-2016 seasonal averages. In a warming climate, most grid points over Europe exhibit a positive trend in T2m and Z500, and the anomalies – both for reforecast and verification data – are more likely to be negative at the beginning of the period, and positive at the end.

The present section discusses the role played by the climate trend on the discrimination metric D of ACC_{pm} forecasting the actual ACC. Table 2 compares the discrimination metric D of ACC_{pm} for Z500 and T2m, before and after the linear trend on the period 1994-2016 has been removed from the anomalies in reforecast and ERA5 reference data. Note that detrending is applied to each grid point and each season separately before the ACCs are computed. Table 2 shows that there is drop in the confidence index proficiency at discriminating the quality of two forecasts when considering detrended data: the drop is about 5% for Z500, and 2% for T2m, even though the performance remains significant after detrending.

The impact of the positive trend in data can be explained by looking at the values of ACC_{pm} and ACC across the 1994-2016 period. This is summarized in Figure 4, which shows the median values of T2m ACC (in blue) and T2m ACC_{pm} (in red) for each year (i.e median of the 12 reforecasts issued that year). Non-detrended and detrended data are both represented, in full and dashed lines respectively. In the non-detrended data, the highest ACC values are found at the beginning and the end of the period, thanks to the trend that enables the reforecasts to show the same sign of anomalies as the observations (negative at the beginning, positive at the end). The same remark holds true for the ACCs between the ensemble members, and consequently for their average ACC_{pm} , which also shows higher values at the beginning and the end of the reforecast period. On the contrary, when considering detrended T2m data, there are no privileged periods with systematically higher values of ACC and ACC_{pm} . As a result, ACC_{pm} is more closely linked to ACC when using non-detrended data than when using detrended data.

	Non-detrended data	Detrended data
Z500	61.4*	56.4*
T2m	59.3*	57.5*

Table 2: Discrimination metric D for ACC_{pm} predicting the actual ACC verification score for Z500 and T2m. The domain for computation of ACC is the Euro-Atlantic domain for Z500, and Europe (land grid points only) for T2m. The discrimination metric D is indicated with a * when significant at the 95% level. The sample is the full reforecast (size 23 years x 12 initializations = 276).

Median ACC values per reforecast year

Figure 4: Median of T2m ACC (in blue) and T2m ACC_{pm} (in red) over the 12 initializations of each reforecast year. Solid lines: raw T2m anomalies. Dashed lines: detrended T2m anomalies.

Whether confidence in the forecast should be expressed from non-detrended or detrended data depends on the users' needs. While the ACC_{pm} confidence index from non-detrended data answers the question "Is the forecast correctly predicting the pattern of anomalies relative to the static 1994-2016 climatology?", the counterpart from detrended data answers the question "Is the forecast correctly predicting the pattern of anomalies that is due to internal variability only?". In a real-time context, if the purpose is to anticipate the score of the current forecast - that does include a trend effect - the ACC_{pm} on non-detrended data will be more appropriate. However, if the purpose is to compare the current forecast to a previous one issued in a different season or year, a confidence index based on detrended data is more relevant.

5.3 Is the confidence index better for specific seasons?

To answer this additional question, we propose to split the reforecast sample into four groups such that the target season at lead time 1-month is mostly included in meteorological winter, spring, summer and autumn (boreal seasons). The four groups are therefore:

- Winter target: reforecasts initialized in October, November and December, respectively targeting the NDJ, DJF and JFM seasons at lead-time 1
- Spring target: reforecasts initialized in January, February and March, respectively targeting the FMA, MAM and AMJ seasons at lead-time 1
- Summer target: reforecasts initialized in April, May and June, respectively targeting the MJJ, JJA and JAS seasons at lead-time 1
- Autumn target: reforecasts initialized in July, August and September, respectively targeting the ASO, SON and OND seasons at lead-time 1

Figure 5: Discrimination metric D of the ACC_{pm} confidence index predicting the actual ACC verification score (reference: ERA5) depending on the predicted season. The domain for computation of ACC is the Euro-Atlantic domain for Z500, and Europe (land grid points only) for T2m and RR. The discrimination metric D is indicated with a * when significant at the 95% level.

Figure 5 provides the discrimination metric D of the ACC_{pm} confidence index over these four sub-samples of reforecasts, for the three variables Z500, T2m and RR. The values of D over the full re-forecast from Figure 2 and Table 2 are also shown as a reminder. In the case of Z500 and T2m, the analysis is performed on both non-detrended and detrended data. Figure 5 shows that the discrimination ability of the Z500 ACC_{pm} confidence index is not strongly sensitive to the seasonal cycle. On the contrary, the discrimination of the T2m ACC_{pm} exhibits a seasonal behaviour: it peaks in autumn and summer for non-detrended data, and in winter for detrended data. Detrending has a strong impact on the discrimination ability, decreasing it for all seasons but winter. This can be related to:

- the stronger warming trend around the summer season
- the better ability of seasonal forecasts to predict the internal variability in winter than in other seasons

This shows that the trend effect explains most of the performance of the T2m ACC_{pm} on non-detrended data in summer, autumn and spring. The reason is the same as that explained in Figure 4. The poor performance on detrended data during those seasons shows that the confidence index is hardly able to predict how good the forecast of internal variability will be. On the contrary, in winter, proficiency of the confidence index is satisfactory and is not related to the trend. Finally, when it comes to precipitation, the discrimination of the RR ACC_{pm} confidence also shows a seasonal cycle, where the highest values are attained in spring and winter.

The overall result of this seasonal analysis is that the ACC_{pm} confidence index approach is most relevant when applied to winter forecasts. It is known to be the most predictable period of the year for seasonal forecasts, and this shows it is also the period when agreement across ensemble members is the most closely related to the ability to predict the internal variability.

5.4 Can we define a cross-variable confidence index?

The previous sections investigated tailored confidence indices for the spatial pattern of one specific variable. However, confidence in the forecast of one variable is presumably not independent from confidence in the forecast of another one. In a real-time forecasting context, a single index may be desirable to summarize how “good” the forecast is expected to be in anticipating multiple aspects of the seasonal climate.

In this section, we intend to propose such an index, by choosing a variable for which the ACC_{pm} confidence index is a good predictor of the actual ACC of the other variables. Table 3 indicates the discrimination metrics D between the ACC_{pm} of one variable and the verification ACC of another one. Note that some cases have been excluded as non-relevant.

It stands out from Table 3 that agreement among the multi-model ensemble members in terms of Z500 is also connected with the actual forecast performance in terms of T2m and precipitation. This is not fully surprising as the anomalies of atmospheric circulation in the Euro-Atlantic sector have an impact on European temperature and precipitation. To further explore this point, Figure 6 shows the seasonal dependence of the Z500 ACC_{pm} discrimination ability while predicting the ACCs of T2m and RR. Figure 6 is the counterpart of last two panels of Figure 5 and the main features in terms of

seasonal dependence are quite similar, such as the better discrimination of winter T2m ACC with detrended data compared to non-detrended data, or the better discrimination of RR ACC in spring and winter when we use the detrended Z500 ACC_{pm}. Therefore, Figure 6 confirms that ACC_{pm} based on Z500 may represent the confidence in the spatial patterns of T2m and RR as well.

	Z500 ACC	Detrended Z500 ACC	T2m ACC	Detrended T2m ACC	RR ACC
Z500 ACC _{pm}	61.4*		61.2*		54.4*
Detrended Z500 ACC _{pm}		56.4*		56.8*	56.7*
T2m ACC _{pm}	58.7*		59.3*		50.3
Detrended T2m ACC _{pm}		56*		57.5*	53.8
RR ACC _{pm}					55*

Table 3: Discrimination metric D when ACC_{pm} computed from one variable (line) is predicting the actual ACC verification score of another variable (column). The domain for computation of ACC is the Euro-Atlantic domain for Z500, and Europe (land grid points only) for T2m. The discrimination metric D is indicated with a * when significant at the 95% level. The sample is the full reforecast (size 23 years x 12 initializations = 276).

Figure 6: Discrimination metric D of the ACC_{pm} confidence index based on Z500 predicting the actual ACC verification score (reference: ERA5) for T2m and RR, depending on the predicted season. The domain for computation of the Z500 ACC_{pm} is the Euro-Atlantic domain, while it is Europe (land grid points only) for the actual ACC of T2m and RR. The discrimination metric D is indicated with a * when significant at the 95% level.

5.5 Retained approach for confidence in seasonal forecasts of spatial patterns

From the previous sections, we retain that the ACC_{pm}-based approach provides a relevant first-guess indicator of the actual ACC forecast score, as it shows limited but significant ability to indicate whether one real-time forecast should be better than another past forecast. However, it remains better suited to winter forecasts than to other seasons.

For the sake of simplicity in an operational context, our suggestion is to use one confidence index among the following options from Table 4, depending on the purpose:

- In order to summarize the multi-variable expected performance for the European climate, the ACC_{pm} based on detrended Z500 should be used. Detrending enables to have a fair comparison between forecasts from different seasons or different years.

- In order to forecast the expected ACC of one specific variable for a given real-time forecast, the indices to be used are listed in Table 4. The main point is to choose an index that is also well calibrated with the actual ACC value.

Purpose	Confidence index to use
Summarizing the multi-variable confidence	Detrended Z500 ACC _{pm}
Forecasting real-time Z500 ACC	Z500 ACC _{pm}
Forecasting real-time T2m ACC	T2m ACC _{pm}
Forecasting real-time RR ACC	Detrended Z500 ACC _{pm} after linear calibration

Table 4: Summary of the most relevant ACC_{pm}-based confidence index depending on the application.

6. Taking into account a physical driver: the case of ENSO

Physical phenomena that are robust sources of seasonal predictability may bring confidence in a forecast when they are at play in the initial conditions. Indeed, seasonal forecasting systems are likely to make better predictions when a strong driver is constraining the state of the atmosphere similarly in the real world and in the model. For this reason, such physical drivers are often supposed to provide “windows of opportunity”, when forecasts perform better than average (Mariotti et al, 2020).

Leveraging physical drivers to define a confidence index has not been our main focus in Task 4.3, neither in M4.3.1 nor in this D4.3.1 deliverable. The reasons are the following:

- 1) If there is a strong physical driver at play, its influence is presumably included indirectly in our approach based on agreement between models and members, as it should affect similarly all members from the multi-model ensemble.
- 2) Due to rarity and limitation to specific seasons, some physical drivers affecting the European climate occur a small number of time in the reforecast sample, and are therefore difficult to leverage automatically in a confidence index. For instance, Sudden Stratospheric Warmings do have an impact on Europe’s surface climate in the following season, but they only occur in winter and there are few of them across the 1994-2016 period.

Yet, we propose to investigate the above reason #1 that agreement between the multi-model ensemble members already contains all the information about a physical driver constraining the future seasonal state of the atmosphere. We focus on the case of ENSO, by analyzing whether the ENSO state brings insight on the future forecast performance that would not already be taken into account by the ACC_{pm} confidence index. For this, we consider the monthly mean SST anomaly in the

Niño3.4 region from HadISST data¹ in the month preceding the initialization of each reforecast, noted N34. The preceding month is used so that N34 would be available in a real-time context.

Table 5 shows the Pearson correlation of the absolute value of N34 against the actual verification ACC on the one hand, and against the “perfect model” ACC_{pm} on the other hand. The absolute value of N34 is chosen so as to investigate the relationship of ACC with strong ENSO events, irrespective of the La Niña or El Niño phase. The key message from Table 5 is that the “perfect model” ACC_{pm} is more strongly associated to the intensity of ENSO than the actual ACC score. It is especially striking for Z500, for which the true ACC is not correlated to ENSO intensity while ACC_{pm} is. This result goes in favor of the assumption that the ENSO driving signal is already widely taken into account in ACC_{pm}. More precisely, the connection between ACC_{pm} and the ENSO state is presumably too strong compared to the actual ENSO-related predictability of the atmosphere.

	ACC	ACC _{pm}
T2m	0.21*	0.24*
Detrended T2m	0.27*	0.35*
Z500	0.05	0.52*
Detrended Z500	0.03	0.71*

Table 5: Pearson correlations of the absolute value of N34 with the actual ACC verification score (reference: ERA5) and the ACC_{pm}, for the variables indicated in each line. N34 is the monthly mean SST anomaly in the Niño3.4 region in the month preceding the initialization of the seasonal forecasts. The sample is the full reforecast (size 23 years x 12 initializations = 276). The Pearson correlation is indicated with a * when significant at the 95% level.

7. Relationship between grid point and spatial confidence indices

While the ACC_{pm} approach is a novelty of the present deliverable, Milestone M4.3.1 also addressed the issue of providing one single confidence index for a spatial field. In M4.3.1, one proposed solution is to use the confidence indices at each grid point and average them over the domain of interest (i.e land grid points over Europe). The reader is invited to refer to Section 5.1 in M4.3.1 for more details. To summarize, the grid-point confidence index from M4.3.1 corresponds to the probability of the most likely tercile category in the ensemble, and the spatial average of these grid-point con-

¹ <https://psl.noaa.gov/data/timeseries/month/Nino34/>

fidence indices is evaluated against the percentage of grid points where this tercile category is correct.

Table 6 proposes to quantify how well the new ACC_{pm} spatial confidence index performs when evaluated by the M4.3.1 standards, i.e how well it can predict the percentage of grid points where the forecast tercile category is correct. For the sake of brevity, only forecasts of temperature over Europe are considered. However, in agreement with Section 5.5, we consider not only the ACC_{pm} based on temperature but also the one based on Z500 which is intended to be the reference one.

Although the percentage of correct grid points is more closely related to the spatial average of the previous M4.3.1 index, we note that the ACC_{pm} -based indices are also relevant predictors of how well the multi-model seasonal forecast will perform at grid point level.

	Spatial mean of M4.3.1 confidence index	T2m ACC_{pm}	Detrended T2m ACC_{pm}	Z500 ACC_{pm}	Detrended Z500 ACC_{pm}
M4.3.1 score T2m	78%*	76%*		67%*	
M4.3.1 score Detrended T2m	74%*		71%*		61%*

Table 6: Discrimination metric D of various spatial confidence indices (columns) against the ratio of European grid points where the tercile category of T2m (top row) or detrended T2m (bottom row) is correctly predicted by the multi-model seasonal forecast. The sample is the full reforecast (size 23 years x 12 initializations = 276). The discrimination metric D is indicated with a * when significant at the 95% level.

8. An overview on real-time cases

Although it has not been experimented in real-time so far, we now propose to examine how the ACC_{pm} confidence index approach would have performed in recent real-time seasonal forecast cases issued between November 2022 and June 2024. The thick black curve from Figure 7 shows the ACCs of the non-detrended T2m multi-model forecasts over Europe for these start dates, verified against ERA5. A possible interpretation of this curve is that the ACC of current T2m forecasts has a high baseline around 0.85 (upper dashed line), but experiences a strong decrease around specific periods (spring 2023, winter 2023-2024). Following the results of Section 5.2, the high baseline can be partly attributed to the warming trend. As for the periods of lower ACC, they can be traced in the Météo-France seasonal verification bulletins, and attributed to cold anomalies that occurred over a specific region of the European continent but where not forecast by the models:

- i) In the spring 2023, the atmospheric circulation over Europe had an unpredicted meridional component that brought cold conditions in the Eastern Mediterranean.
- ii) In the winter 2023-2024, Scandinavia experienced cold anomalies related to an unforecast excess of days with negative-NAO circulation, combined to a deficit of blocking days.

Figure 7: Values of the multi-model T2m ACC (verification against ERA5) and the ACC_{pm} of non-detrended T2m, non-detrended Z500 and detrended Z500 for the 20 real-time seasonal forecasts issued between November 2022 and June 2024. The multi-model has 304 members in real-time (see Table 1). The discrimination metric D is indicated with a * when significant at the 95% level. Note that all ACC_{pm} curves have been rescaled to be comparable to the actual ACC for clarity.

The blue and red curves respectively indicate the non-detrended T2m and Z500 ACC_{pm} confidence indices during the same period, while the orange curve is for ACC_{pm} of detrended Z500, previously defined as the reference confidence index (Section 5.5). Note that all ACC_{pm} curves have been rescaled to be comparable to the actual ACC for clarity, but that the true values are lower and show less variability. Among the three ACC_{pm} indices, the one based on detrended Z500 is by far the most relevant to infer the actual forecast performance during this period: it is correctly phased to the minimum ACCs of the March 2023 and October 2023 initializations, and it is the only one to show a significant discrimination metric D over the sample. This is surprising since the actual T2m ACC under study is based on non-detrended data, but this is an additional argument to choose the ACC_{pm} based on detrended Z500 as the reference confidence index. In the meantime, the ACC_{pm} based on

non-detrended Z500 data detects reasonably well the low-skill forecasts around winter 2023-2024, but fails to suggest the forecast bust in spring 2023. The opposite can be said of ACC_{pm} based on non-detrended T2m, which suggests a decrease in ACC in spring 2023 but is out of phase for the 2023-2024 winter.

9. Conclusion

Task 4.3 of Work Package 4 from the C3S2-370-MF contract has explored several approaches to define a confidence index of multi-model seasonal forecasts over the European continent. These approaches are all based on quantifying the agreement between the ensemble members of the multi-model, originating from 6 different modeling centers. A first milestone (M4.3.1) suggested to consider the forecast probability of the most likely tercile category as an information of confidence at grid point level. The present deliverable provides a final version of the index that is intended to indicate how “good” a real-time forecast will be at predicting the spatial patterns of 500 hPa geopotential, near-surface temperature and precipitation anomalies in the next season.

The index is based on the mean of the “perfect model” spatial correlations between each ensemble member and the ensemble mean, noted ACC_{pm} . Although there can be as many confidence indices as variables under consideration, we have shown that the agreement between ensemble members on the Euro-Atlantic detrended Z500 pattern can also be used as a confidence index for surface variables over Europe, and will be considered as the main confidence index in further experimentation. Moreover, the strong connection of this index with the intensity of ENSO has shown that the agreement between ensemble members is implicitly taking into account the strong drivers of seasonal climate as a source of confidence in the forecast. Regarding the ability of the retained index to “forecast forecast skill”, it appears to be modest but significant, as shown by the success at detecting the worst predictions among the latest real-time forecasts. Future plans at Météo-France now include a real-time experimentation of the ACC_{pm} -based confidence index on a monthly basis for the seasonal forecast bulletins.

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